

Synthesis, Anticonvulsant and Analgesic Activities of some New Fluorine containing 1,3,5-Trisubstituted-hydantoin

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Fifteen new fluorine containing Mannich bases derived from 1,5-disubstituted-aryl-hydantoin have been synthesised by treating the appropriate 1,5-disubstituted-aryl-hydantoin with secondary amine and formaldehyde in ethanol. Seven 1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin were treated with chloroacetyl chloride and the resulting 3-chloroacetyl-derivatives converted into the corresponding 3-dialkylaminoacetyl-1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin on treatment with secondary amines. Representative compounds have been screened for their anticonvulsant and analgesic activities. S.A.R. studies show that morpholinomethyl or chloroacetyl group at 3-position displays greater anticonvulsive activity as compared to compounds containing hydrogen, or dimethylaminomethyl or diethylaminomethyl group.

HYDANTOINS and allied derivatives are of great interest to medicinal chemists due to their diverse biological activities, like lowering of blood sugar level in mammals¹, antiarrhythmic^{2,3}, antitubercular⁴, antiinflammatory⁵, antitumor^{6,7} and anticonvulsant properties^{8,9}. Various spirohydantoin derivatives including those with a C₁₂-ring are being used as antidiabetics and anticonvulsants¹⁰⁻¹². A perusal of literature revealed sufficient scope for further studies on bioactive fluorinated hydantoin and allied derivatives. We have therefore undertaken a comprehensive programme for developing new biologically active fluorinated hydantoin and have already reported the synthesis of seventeen new fluorine containing 1,5-disubstituted-hydantoin¹⁴ and as a part of this programme, we now wish to report the synthesis and biological activities of fifteen new Mannich bases derived from 1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin and seven new 3-dialkylaminoacetyl-1,5-diarylhydantoin.

Results and Discussion

1,5-Disubstituted-arylhydantoin (3a-3m) exhibited two ir absorption peaks in the region of 1770-1780 (C=O absorption at 4-position) and 1710-1720 cm⁻¹ (due to C=O absorption at 2-position). A broad absorption is noticed between 3040-3080 cm⁻¹ due to NH at 3-position (characteristic of CONHCO in the cyclic system). The pmr spectra of 3a-3m exhibit resonance signal in the region of δ 8.58-6.78 (ArH). The NH of these compounds exhibit broad, weak and variable resonance signal at δ 5.76-9.24 (determined by D₂O exchange) and the tertiary methine group at 5.32-5.78.

Treatment of 3a-3m with formaldehyde and secondary amine in ethanol afforded the desired Mannich bases, 4a-4o. The formation of 4 is confirmed by complete disappearance of NH resonance

- (3a) Ar=C₆H₅; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3b) Ar=4-F.C₆H₄; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3c) Ar=4-F.C₆H₄; Ar'=4-CH₃.C₆H₄
 (3d) Ar=4-F.C₆H₄; Ar'=4-Cl.C₆H₄
 (3e) Ar=4-F,3-OH₂.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3f) Ar=2-F,5-OH₂.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3g) Ar=2-Cl,4-F.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3h) Ar=3-Cl,4-F.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3i) Ar=3-Cl,4-F.C₆H₃; Ar'=4-Cl.C₆H₄
 (3j) Ar=3-Cl,4-F.C₆H₃; Ar'=4-OH₂.C₆H₃
 (3k) Ar=2,5-F₂.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3l) Ar=2,3,4,5,6-F₅.C₆H; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (3m) Ar=3-F,4-OH₂.C₆H₃; Ar'=C₆H₅
 (4) and (6) R-N-R'=Morpholino, diethylamino and dimethylamino groups.

Scheme 1

signal at δ 5.76-9.24 and appearance of new resonance signal centred at 4.54-4.64 methylene group (N-CH₂-N). In addition to this, 4a-4i exhibited resonance signals centred at δ 3.68-3.70

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CHARACTERISTIC DATA OF 3-DIALKYLAMINO-5-SUBSTITUTED-ARYL-1-PHENYLHYDANTOIN (4)

Compd. no.	Substituents in Ar	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R} \\ \diagup \\ \text{N} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{R}_1 \end{array}$	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
4a	H	Morpholino	80	167	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	68.21 (68.37)	5.78 (5.98)	11.86 (11.96)
4b	4-F	Morpholino	74	178	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O ₂	64.98 (65.04)	5.38 (5.42)	11.27 (11.38)
4c	2-Cl, 4-F	Morpholino	70	135	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.44 (59.47)	4.58 (4.70)	10.31 (10.40)
4d	3-Cl, 4-F	Morpholino	78	150	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.58 (59.47)	4.60 (4.70)	10.58 (10.40)
4e	2-F, 5-OH ₂	Morpholino	85	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ FN ₂ O ₂	65.81 (65.79)	5.54 (5.74)	10.71 (10.96)
4f	4-F, 3-OH ₂	Morpholino	80	127	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ FN ₂ O ₂	65.58 (65.79)	5.61 (5.74)	10.82 (10.96)
4g	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	Morpholino	68	82	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ FN ₂ O ₄	63.25 (63.15)	5.41 (5.51)	10.41 (10.52)
4h	2,5-F ₂	Morpholino	70	185	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂	62.31 (62.01)	4.78 (4.90)	10.62 (10.85)
4i	2,3,5,6-PentaF	Morpholino	45	169	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ F ₅ N ₂ O ₂	54.41 (54.29)	3.51 (3.61)	9.41 (9.50)
4j	2-Cl, 4-F	Diethylamino	78	110	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂	61.82 (61.61)	5.21 (5.39)	10.56 (10.78)
4k	3-Cl, 4-F	Diethylamino	80	125	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂	61.42 (61.61)	5.21 (5.39)	10.48 (10.78)
4l	4-F, 3-OH ₂	Diethylamino	65	210	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ FN ₂ O ₂	68.41 (68.20)	6.41 (6.50)	11.48 (11.38)
4m	2-Cl, 4-F	Dimethylamino	67	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.55 (59.75)	4.61 (4.70)	11.51 (11.61)
4n	3-Cl, 4-F	Dimethylamino	80	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.85 (59.75)	4.81 (4.70)	11.42 (11.61)
4o	4-F, 3-OH ₂	Dimethylamino	71	235	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ FN ₂ O ₂	66.51 (66.86)	5.71 (5.84)	12.21 (12.31)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND CHARACTERISTIC DATA OF 3-CHLOROACETYL-1,5-DISUBSTITUTED-ARYLHYDANTOIN (5)

Compd. no.	Substituent in Ar	Substituent in Ar ¹	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
5a	H	H	187	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	61.80 (62.10)	3.72 (3.95)	8.35 (8.52)
5b	4-F	H	187	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClFN ₂ O ₂	58.77 (58.95)	3.50 (3.46)	7.95 (8.09)
5c	4-F	4-OH ₂	180	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.75 (59.91)	3.55 (3.88)	7.35 (7.76)
5d	4-F	4-Cl	197	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ FN ₂ O ₂	53.25 (53.54)	2.75 (2.88)	7.20 (7.34)
5e	3-Cl, 4-F	H	153	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ FN ₂ O ₂	53.30 (53.54)	2.70 (2.88)	7.25 (7.34)
5f	3-Cl, 4-F	4-Cl	165	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ FN ₂ O ₂	48.85 (49.09)	2.25 (2.40)	6.35 (6.78)
5g	3-Cl, 4-F	4-OH ₂	130	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ FN ₂ O ₂	54.50 (54.68)	3.10 (3.29)	6.95 (7.08)

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND CHARACTERISTIC DATA OF 3-DIALKYLAMINOACETYL-1,5-DISUBSTITUTED-ARYLHYDANTOIN (6)

Sl. no.	Substituent in Ar	Substituent in Ar ¹	$\begin{array}{c} \text{R} \\ \diagup \\ \text{N} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{R}^1 \end{array}$	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
6a	H	H	Diethylamino	160	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂	68.88 (69.04)	6.20 (6.30)	11.40 (11.50)
6b	4-F	H	Diethylamino	165	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ FN ₂ O ₂	65.60 (65.79)	5.65 (5.74)	10.85 (10.96)
6c	3-Cl, 4-F	4-Cl	Morpholino	201	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ FN ₂ O ₂	53.95 (54.29)	3.65 (3.61)	9.80 (9.50)
6d	3-Cl, 4-F	4-OH ₂	Dimethylamino	185	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.15 (59.47)	4.32 (4.70)	10.20 (10.40)
6e	3-Cl, 4-F	4-OH ₂	Morpholino	182	73	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂	59.11 (59.25)	4.65 (4.71)	9.30 (9.42)

(4H, dd, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$) and 2.55-2.62 (4H, dd, $\text{CH}_2-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ of morpholino group, protons). In compounds 4j-4l, a triplet and a quartet centred at δ 0.60-1.52 (6H, t) and 2.42-2.74 (4H, q) respectively, have been assigned to diethylamino group $(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}-$ protons.

Treatment of 3a-3d and 3h-3j with chloroacetyl chloride in toluene gave 3-chloroacetyl-1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoins (5a-5g). These compounds have been characterised by appearance of additional new resonance signal as singlet at δ 2.1-2.2 corresponding to the protons of COCH_2Cl group. Further confirmation for the formation of the compounds 5a-5g has been obtained by appearance of an additional band in the region of $1610-1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$). Compounds 5a-5d and 5g on treatment with secondary amine gave compounds 6a-6e, the analytical and spectral data of which are in harmony with the proposed structures of 6.

In addition to these, all compounds exhibited characteristic $\text{Ar}_{\text{C-F}}$ absorption peaks between $1260-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Mass spectral studies: Perusal of literature revealed that no mass spectral studies on hydantoins were reported¹⁵ till 1970, and subsequent¹⁶, there is only one reference available to date concerning such studies¹⁶. Keeping this in view, we now report the mass spectral studies of Mannich bases derived from 1,4-disubstituted-arylhydantoins. Mannich bases 4c, 4e, 4f and 4j were subjected to mass spectral studies. Under electron impact all

these compounds gave prominent molecular ions at m/z 403/405, 383, 383 and 303/305, respectively. The molecular ions corresponding to 4c and 4j showed prominent isotopic peaks due to presence of one chlorine atom in 3 : 1 ratios [4c, 403 (26.40); 405 (8.80) and 4j, 303 (78.4); 305 (26.10)]. In case of 4c, 4e, 4f the base peaks are at m/z 100 corresponding to morpholinomethylene cation, while in case of 4j the base peak is at m/z 86 which is attributed due to diethylaminomethylene cation. A typical mass spectral fragmentation (4e) is given in the Scheme 2. The molecular ion (m/z 383) of compound 4e fragmented under electron impact by various routes. In route a, the molecular ion eli-

minates a neutral moiety $-(\text{Ph}-\text{N}-\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{N})$ to give a cation radical II at m/z 150. In route b, the molecular ion eliminates a radical corresponding to m/z 283 to afford the morpholinomethylene cation II at 100 (100%), which is stabilised by resonance. In route c, molecular ion undergoes a hydrogen transfer accompanied by elimination of a radical

corresponding to m/z 99 $-\text{[CH-N]}$ to provide cation IV (m/z 284). The cation IV, in turn fragmented to cations V and VII, respectively. The cation V further eliminates a neutral moiety corresponding to m/z 137 to yield phenyl cation (m/z 77).

Scheme 2

TABLE 4—PROBABILITY FACTOR OF SOME NEW FLUORINE CONTAINING 1,5-DI- AND 1,3,5-TRISUBSTITUTED-HYDANTOINS AT 3 DOSES OTHER THAN THREE COMPLETE TONIC EXTENSION NOT OCCURRED

Compd. no.	Dose orally mg/kg	Control, t s X ₁	After 4 h of drug administration (t) X ₂	Protection (X ₁ - X ₂) = X	S.D. (±)	S.E.	t(±) = $\frac{X}{S.E.}$	P (Probability factor)
3b	200	13.15	8.35	5.80	3.24	1.45	3.99	0.01
	250	14.00	5.00	9.00	2.33	1.04	8.63	0.001
3e	300	13.50	9.10	5.40	1.63	0.73	7.38	0.001
3f	400	13.50	12.0	1.50	1.17	0.52	2.86	0.02
3g	100	14.50	5.50	9.00	0.79	0.35	25.40	0.001
3h	100	12.50	8.15	4.35	1.50	0.67	6.40	0.001
	200	13.00	7.00	5.00	1.34	0.60	8.28	0.001
3i	400	13.50	6.80	6.70	0.63	0.35	18.83	0.001
4c	100	12.50	6.80	5.70	2.72	1.22	4.66	0.001
4m	300	13.70	4.80	8.90	0.91	0.41	21.68	0.001
4j	300	10.40	9.20	1.20	0.97	0.43	2.74	0.05
	400	9.80	3.30	6.50	3.02	1.35	4.79	0.001
4g	200	15.50	13.50	2.00	0.79	0.35	5.64	0.001
	300	15.90	13.40	2.50	1.41	0.63	3.95	0.01
	400	14.50	11.10	3.40	1.55	0.69	4.88	0.001
4d	100	14.00	3.60	10.40	1.57	0.70	14.78	0.001
5a	200	13.40	6.50	6.90	2.53	1.13	6.07	0.01
5b	100	12.80	5.10	7.70	1.09	0.48	15.71	0.001
5d	200	12.50	6.10	6.40	1.08	0.48	13.20	0.001
5c	400	13.10	18.50	5.40	1.54	0.68	7.83	0.01

* Inference : Significant for all compounds.

In route *d*, molecular ion fragmented to cation V by eliminating a radical moiety corresponding to

of molecular ion (I) in route *e* begins with transfer of a hydrogen accompanied with the loss of neutral moiety (HNCO) to afford cation radical VIII. This in turn eliminates a neutral moiety (m/z 144) yielding a cation IX (m/z 196).

Biological screening : Compounds 3b, 3e, 3f, 3g, 3h, 3i, 4c, 4d, 4g, 4j, 4m, 5a-5c and 5d were evaluated for their anticonvulsant and analgesic activities by the method of Swingard¹⁷ and by tail-pinch method¹⁸, respectively. All compounds show significant anticonvulsant activity. The probability factor (P) of all these compounds varies within < 0.001 to 0.05 (Table 4). None of these compounds show significant analgesic activity. The depressive activity was the most common feature exhibited by these compounds. 5b containing fluorine at 4'-position of the C-5 aryl moiety showed two-fold anticonvulsant activity as compared to non-fluorinated analog, 5a. It is interesting to note that introduction of chlorine at 2'- and 3'-position in C-5 fluoroaryl moiety (3g and 3h) increases the anticonvulsant activity sharply. However, effect is more pronounced when chlorine is being substituted at 2'- (3g) rather than at 3'-position (3h) of C-5 fluoroaryl moiety. In contrast to this, introduction of electron donating group (e.g. CH₃) at 3'- or 5'-position of C-5 fluoroaryl moiety (3e and 3f) decreases the anticonvulsant activity. Replacement of hydrogen at position N-1 of the hydantoin

ring by 4-chlorophenyl group (5d) results in two-fold reduction of the anticonvulsant activity, while replacement of this hydrogen (at position N-1) by 4-tolyl group (5c) preserves the anticonvulsant activity. It is interesting to note that replacement of hydrogen (at position N-3 of the hydantoin ring) chloroacetyl group (5b) and by morpholinomethyl moieties (4c, 4d and 4g) results in sharp increase of anticonvulsant activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected (capillary apparatus). Pmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker HX-90 (CDCl₃/TMS as internal standard) spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on Kratos MS-30 and MS-50 mass spectrometers. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Tlc analysis was carried out on silica gel plates (60 F₂₅₄, E. Merck) and column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (60, E. Merck).

Fluorinated arylglyoxal and 1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin : The compounds were prepared by the method reported earlier¹⁴.

3-Dialkylaminomethyl-1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin (4) : A mixture of 1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoin (0.01 mol), secondary amine (0.012 mol) and formaldehyde (0.015 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 4 h. On cooling a sticky product was obtained which solidified on addition of ice-cold water. The solid product thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 3) and gave single spot on tlc in various solvent systems. The characteristic and analytical data for all compounds (4a-4o) are recorded in Table 1.

3-Chloroacetyl-1,5-disubstituted arylhydantoins (5): 1,5-Disubstituted-arylhydantoin (0.068 mol) was refluxed with chloroacetylchloride (0.070 mol) in toluene for 8 h. The dark brown reaction mixture on cooling, gave the desired product which was filtered, washed several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and recrystallised from appropriate solvent. All compounds gave single spot on tlc in various solvent systems. In some cases, the desired product was further purified by column chromatography (silica gel; benzene-petroleum ether, 3 : 1) to yield analytical sample. The characteristic and analytical data for all compounds (5a-5g) are recorded in Table 2.

3-Dialkylaminoacetyl-1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoins (6): The appropriate secondary amine (0.015 mol) in ether (25-40 ml) was added dropwise to a ethereal solution of 3-chloro-1,5-disubstituted-arylhydantoins at 0°. The resulting mixture was refluxed^{1v} for 8 h to give the desired product, which was filtered and recrystallised from solvent ether. All compounds gave single spot on tlc in various solvent systems. The characteristics and analytical data for all compounds (6a-6e) are recorded in Table 3.

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